

**ASSESSING NURSES' JOB SATISFACTION AND ITS EFFECTS ON
PATIENT EXPERIENCE AND QUALITY OF CARE IN NNAMDI
AZIKIWE TEACHING HOSPITAL****Ifeoma Chioma Eze**

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Abstract

Nurses are the largest workforce in healthcare facilities, providing 50% - 80% of healthcare services. They play important role in providing quality care to patients, which is important in healthcare. This study determined job satisfaction, patient satisfaction and quality of care of nurses in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State. A descriptive cross-sectional survey was used. A self-administered questionnaire was used to obtain information from 208 nurses, 138 patients and 36 head nurses using simple randomization technique. A pilot testing was carried out with a reliability index of 0.81. Data analysis was performed using Statistical Software for Social Sciences (SPSS) database version 25. Chi square was used to test the significance hypotheses of $p < 0.05$. The majority of nurses 82 (39.42%) were between ages 41-50 while most of them, 48 (23.08%) had between 11-15 years of experience. Most of the recruited patients (43.48%) were between the ages of 31-46 years and most respondents were female (52.17%). The results also show that the majority of nurses (55.3%) were dissatisfied with their jobs. 84.8% of the patients were satisfied with the quality of nursing care. According to head nurses reports, nurses provided quality care to patients. Communication and team building, training, leadership and management, salary, work itself, work environment, interpersonal relationship were significantly positively associated with overall job satisfaction. Job satisfaction of nurses in this research area was slightly low. On the other hand, patients are quite satisfied with the level of care. Despite nurses' job satisfaction, they still provide quality care to patients. It recommended that hospital management and government should consider all components of job satisfaction.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Patient satisfaction, Quality of care

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is important in the daily life of the employees and forms the basis of employee turnover among healthcare professionals. Job Satisfaction is how people feel about their jobs, whether they like their jobs (satisfied) or dislike (dissatisfied). It has a positive impact on nurse's job satisfaction, patient safety, staff performance, productivity, quality of care, organization commitment and profession (Samson-Akpan et al., 2015).

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Job satisfaction is affected by many factors that enable nurses to provide good patient care such as healthy working environment, adequate work, timely and adequate salary, professional development, adequate working hours, friendliness and leadership, appropriate production and quality equipment. It is an important part of employee retention in any organization (Njaka, et al., 2020). Nurses constitute the largest workforce in healthcare facilities and provide 50% - 80% of health care services. They play an important role in healthcare by providing quality care to patients (Mousazadeh, et al., 2019). Patient Satisfaction is how patients feel when using medical services (Amporfrol et al., 2021). Evaluation of care provided to patients is an important determinant and indicator of the quality of health services worldwide (Amporfro et al., 2021; Manzoor et al., 2019). There are many factors that influence patient satisfaction include; access to healthcare services, healthcare providers, finances, government regulations, admission procedures, relationship of healthcare professionals, environment, diagnostic services and communication (Umoke, et al., 2020). Patient satisfaction is essential in improving service quality in healthcare (Amporfro et al., 2021). Quality of care is the degree to which health services are delivered to individuals and communities that meet their health needs and are based on standard professional experiences (Buttel et al., 2007). The development and delivery of quality care is important to reduce the number of people with chronic diseases and prevent premature deaths (Torkula, 2020). Donabedian Theory of Quality of Care proposes three ways to measure quality of care such as the physical environment, patient seeking care and effects of care on patient health status provides the basis for evaluating healthcare services and measuring quality of care (WHO, 2021). According to WHO (2009) stated that some countries need to increase their workforce to 140% to achieve sustainable development goals in Sub-Sahara Africa (Asuquo, et al., 2017). WHO predicts that there will be a medical workforce shortage of 12.9 million by 2035, with the number of healthcare professional falling sharply in Asian countries (47%), Africa (25%) and Europe (1%) (Niskala et al., 2020; Chang et al., 2017). Healthcare systems globally face challenges in recruiting and retaining nurses, which is due to low pay, lack of motivation, inadequate training, lack of respect and therefore job dissatisfaction. These affect the quality of care for patients (Asima et al., 2017; Niskala et al., 2019). About 600 Nigerian healthcare workers voluntarily migrate every year to Western countries, mostly Europe and North American in search of better jobs. As many as 13% of nursing workers move to other countries for better benefits/income, adequate work and environment, leading to decline in healthcare (Kever et al., 2018; Njaka et al., 2020). Industrial disputes among healthcare professionals and incessant strikes, making it difficult for people to access medical services. Compared to other African countries, Nigeria has one of the worst global health indicators and one of the weakest health systems, accounting for 10% of global diseases and a maternal mortality rate of 1350/100,000 live births, the fifth lowest and under five mortality rate of 109/1000 live births (Njaka et al., 2020). Understanding the importance of nurses' satisfaction will improve the quality of care provided to patients and therefore increase patient satisfaction, which is an important factor in healthcare. Hence, this study was to determine nurses' job satisfaction, patients' satisfaction and quality of care in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Anambra State.

The Objectives of the study

1. To determine of nurses' job satisfaction Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State.
2. To identify factors affecting nurses' job satisfaction Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State.
3. To determine patients satisfaction in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State.
4. To identify the factors that influence the quality of nursing care as perceived by the nurse managers in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive cross sectional study was used to determine nurses' job satisfaction, patients' satisfaction and quality of care in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi. The sample size was calculated using Taro Yamane's and Cochran Formulae to select respondents and a simple random technique was used to select participants. The total number of nurses was collected from the Nursing Services Department in Nnamdi Azikiwe Teaching Hospital Nnewi. An adapted self-structured questionnaire was used in data collection. The questionnaire was divided into five sections. Section A: Respondents socio-demographic characteristics, Section B: To determine nurses job satisfaction, Section C: To identify factors that influence nurses job satisfaction, Section D: To determine the patients satisfaction and Section E: To identify factors influencing perceived quality of care as from the nurse managers. Face and content validity was done by two experts to determine the validity of the instrument. A pilot testing was carried out to determine the reliability of the instrument with reliability index of 0.81. Ethical approval was obtained for the study from Nnamdi Azikiwe Teaching Hospital Research Ethics Committee. Verbal consent was obtained from nurses in the wards and inpatients in the wards. Inform consent form were signed by recruited participants. The purpose of the research study was explained to the participants. Data collected with the interval of two months. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics using Statistical Package for Social Science database version 25. The results of the study were presented in frequency and table. Chi square was used to test the hypotheses.

RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the nurses in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State. (n=208)

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
20-30	34	16.35
31-40	66	31.73

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41-50	82	39.42
Above 50 years	26	12.50
Gender		
Female	191	91.83
Male	17	8.17
Marital status		
Divorced	2	0.96
Married	134	64.42
Single	44	21.15
Widowed	28	13.46
Professional rank		
ADNS	39	18.75
CNO	34	16.35
ACNO	14	6.73
PNO	32	15.38
SNO	30	14.42
NO 1	24	11.54
NO 11	35	16.83
Years of experience		
Less than 5 years	33	15.87
Less than 10 years	40	19.23
Less than 15 years	48	23.08
Less than 16 years	1	0.48
Less than 20 years	25	12.02
Less than 25 years	36	17.31
Less than 35 years	25	12.02
Educational qualification		
BNSC	98	47.12
BSC	15	7.21
MASTERS	13	6.25
RN/DIPLOMA	82	39.42

Table 1 above showed that most of the participants (39.42%) were between the ages ranges of 41-50 years, majority (91.83%) were female. Majority of the respondents (64.42%) were married, (18.75%) were in the

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professional rank of assistant director of nursing. Majority (23.08%) had less than 15 years' work experience and most of them (47.12%) had bachelor in nursing science.

Table 2: Degree of nurses' job satisfaction in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Newwi, Anambra State. (n=208)

JOB SATISFACTION	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Poor satisfaction	115	55.3
Good satisfaction	93	44.7
Total	208	100.0

The above result in table 2 showed that 55.3% of the nurses had poor job satisfaction while 44.7% of the nurses had good job satisfaction.

Table 3: Cross tabulation between factors and levels of job satisfaction in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Newwi, Anambra State.

Variables	X ² -value	p- value
Communication and team building		
My colleagues communicate well.	31.034	0.001
My colleague's first priority is the patient.		0.014
My nurse manager is involved in activities that promote patient care and services.	10.650	0.026
Training		
I receive the necessary training to cope with the problems of patient and their family.	23.230	0.001
Professional development and growth are considered by management.	31.217	0.001
Leadership/ management		
My nurse manager treats me with dignity and respect.	35.649	0.001
The management immensely considered the career opportunities and their growth.	74.322	0.001
Salary		
I am fairly compensated for the work I do.	23.901	0.032
I have enough money to cover my family expenses.	16.469	0.002
Work itself		
Information is conveyed effectively.	26.333	0.001
I do my work to the best of my ability.	8.712	0.032

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Work environment		
The environment is quiet and conducive.	14.172	0.007
Adequate equipment and tools at work place.	26.572	0.001
Interpersonal relationship		
Colleagues at the hospital have good cordial relationship among themselves.	34.603	0.001
Nurse manager and staff can talk freely.	19.039	0.001

Table 4: Socio-demographic characteristics of patients in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State. (n= 138)

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Age		
<=30 years	30	21.74
31-46 years	60	43.48
47-62 years	35	25.36
Above 63 years	13	9.42
Gender		
Female	72	52.17
Male	66	47.83
Marital status		
Divorced	1	0.72
Married	97	70.29
Single	35	25.36
Widowed	5	3.62
Admitted through		
Day case	4	2.90
Emergency	63	45.65
OPD	42	30.43
Referral	29	21.01

Table 4 above showed that majority of patients 63 (43.48%) were within the age range of 31-46 years, 72 (52.17%) were mostly female, 97 (70.29%) were married and most patients 63 (45.65%) were admitted through emergency.

Table 5: Degree of patients' satisfaction in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State.

PATIENTS' SATISFACTION	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Poor satisfaction	21	15.2
Good satisfaction	117	84.8

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Total	138	100.0
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The result in table 5 showed that 84.8% of the patients had good satisfaction while 15.2% of the patients had poor satisfaction.

Table 6: Showing factors influencing quality of care as perceived by nurse managers in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra State. (n= 36)

Factors	Variables	Yes n (%)	No n (%)
Environmental Factors	Adequate lighting in wards/clinic	15 (41.7)	21 (58.3)
	Adequate ventilation of the ward/clinic.	23 (63.9)	13 (36.1)
	Provision and maintenance of quiet environment in the ward/clinic	27 (75.0)	9 (25.0)
	Adequate and appropriate cleanliness of the ward/clinic.	29 (80.6)	7 (19.4)
Organizational Factors	The hospital have large number of nurses to provide quality patient/client.	4 (11.1)	32 (88.9)
	Working with clinically competent nurses.	30 (83.3)	6 (16.7)
	Treatment and medication are provided to patients without delay.	24 (66.7)	12 (33.3)
	Appropriate shift handover within the ward.	33 (91.7)	3 (8.3)
Nurse-Related Factors	Appropriately and timely written patient care plan.	26 (72.2)	10 (27.8)
	Records are kept and maintained effectively by nurses.	32 (88.9)	4 (11.1)
	Nurses are given the opportunity to participate in policy decisions.	9 (25.0)	27 (75.0)
	Career opportunities.	13 (36.1)	23 (63.9)
	Maintaining client/ patient privacy during examination/ procedure.	33 (91.7)	3 (8.3)
	Patient information is kept confidential.	34 (94.4)	2 (5.6)

Table 6 above showed that quality of care perceived by nurse managers showed high mean percentage compliance. This was assigned under the following factors environmental factors (65.3%), organizational factors (63.2%) and nurse-related factors (68.1%).

Hypotheses Testing

HO 1 There is no significant relationship between nurses' job satisfaction and quality of care.

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Job satisfaction	vs		Poor quality of care	Good quality of care
<u>Quality of care</u>	<u>X²-value</u>	<u>p-value</u>		
Poor satisfaction	4 (44.4)	9 (33.3)		
Good satisfaction	5 (55.6)	18 (66.7)	0.361	0.548

Chi square showed no significant relationship between nurses' job satisfaction and quality of care ($X^2= 0.361$, $p>0.05$). Hence, null hypothesis was accepted.

HO 2: There is no significant relationship between patients' satisfaction and quality of care.

Patients' satisfaction	vs		Poor quality of care	Good quality of care
<u>Quality of care</u>	<u>X²-value</u>	<u>p-value</u>		
Poor satisfaction	0 (0.0)	1 (3.7)		
Good satisfaction	9 (100.0)	26 (96.3)	0.342	0.558

Chi square showed no significant relationship between patients' satisfaction and quality of care ($X^2= 0.342$, $p>0.05$). Hence, null hypothesis was accepted.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that most nurses were not satisfied with their jobs. This is consistent with previous findings on the level of job satisfaction by Olajide et al. (2020), Ayalew and colleagues (2019) and Elsherbeny et al. (2018). Furthermore, in the work done by Elsherbeny et al. there was a higher percentage of nurses job dissatisfaction that was found in the study, possibly due to environmental influence as their study was done in Egypt. Another possible reason is that the recruited participants in their study were significantly higher (346 participants) than in our study which may have influenced the final outcome of the level of nurses job satisfaction. Also work done by Olajide et al. (2020) showed a low level of job satisfaction in their study, perhaps due to possibly lower remuneration obtained in state public hospitals compared to federal public hospitals in Nigeria. However, previous findings on the level of nurses job satisfaction in works by Wali et al. (2023); Asuquo et al. (2017) and SamsonAkpan et al. (2015) contradicts with the findings of this study. They found that majority of nurses were satisfied with their jobs. It is important to note that Wali et al. conducted their study in Saudi Arabia which is known to be an oil -rich nation and may have influenced the outcome of their study. Both Asuquo et al. (2017) and Samson-Akpan et al. (2015) findings showed that nurses were moderately satisfied with their jobs. Ndubuisi et al. (2023) found that nurses were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their jobs with a mean score of 30.36. This is not consistent with this study. The study showed that the following factors; communication and team building, training, leadership/management, salary, work itself, work environment, interpersonal relationship significantly influence job satisfaction. Olajide et al. (2020) in their work in Lagos, Nigeria found out that majority (100%) of the respondents were not satisfied with their salary which is consistent with findings in this work. Other

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studies by Asuquo and colleagues (2017), Orukowu et al. (2021), Malalasekare and colleagues (2020), Njaka et al. (2020), Kever et al. (2018) demonstrated that salary is a significant influence of job satisfaction. This is similar with the findings of this study. This may be the reason nurses are leaving the country to source for greener pastures in the western countries. Across the items on the scale on leadership/management, Supraman and colleague (2023), and Archibong (2023) similarly concluded that leadership significantly affect job satisfaction. Their findings are in tandem with the findings in this study. There should be participative leadership/management involvement to ensure job satisfaction of nurses. Previous studies in line with our findings reported that work environment, training and development are likely to reduce nurses' job satisfaction. Orukowu and colleague (2021); Kever et al. (2018) results demonstrated that working environment is a significant factor, which is in line with the study. Also Kabita et al. (2022) demonstrated that environment (88%) affect nurse's job satisfaction. Also according to Malalasekara and colleague (2020) training and development significantly influence job satisfaction. This is consistent with the findings of the study. There should be attempt to improve working environment, as well as trainings for self-development of nurses. Moreover, communication and team building among nurses was revealed to have significant effect on the satisfaction levels of nurses. This in line with Olusegun and colleague (2020) that nurses were grossly dissatisfied with communication flow/administrative roles. Njaka et al. (2020) also demonstrated that communication flows and administrative role significantly affect nurses' job satisfaction. Appropriate communication channels and adequate administrative roles should be ensured to incorporate nurses in health care facilities. Also, work itself was demonstrated to significantly affect job satisfaction. This is consistent with Chegini et al. (2019) that organizational commitment had significant positive relationships with self-efficacy ($P < 0.001$) and job satisfaction ($P < 0.001$). Also Hakami et al. (2020) showed that nurses with job satisfaction have organizational commitment. Ashwaq and colleagues (2022) also demonstrated a significant relationship between overall organizational citizenship behaviour and overall job satisfaction of nurses ($r = 0.354$, $P < 0.01$) which is in line with the study. Finally, interpersonal relationship significantly affect job satisfaction. However, this is consistent with Yiltormanen (2021), Tengah et al. (2019) revealed that nurse-nurse collaboration and relationship among nurses and other employees significantly affect nurse's job satisfaction. Therefore, collaboration among professionals also increases job satisfaction. The findings of this study showed that most of patients were satisfied with nursing care. It is obvious that most respondents consider nurses as the most crucial in healthcare. Majority were satisfied with the information the nurses provided for their recovery, and majority were satisfied that nurses always make them feel comfortable and have empathy about their condition, they were fulfilled that nurses are always ready to meet their needs. Majority stated that nurses are able to do their job which is important for them to recover from illness. Nurses are kind, respectful and always take care of their health. Most were satisfied about nurses gave clear and understandable instructions regarding their diagnosis and treatment. Peace and quiet environment was maintained and nurses reported information about their illness to their families. Patients were satisfied with clear and complete instructions on

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discharge. The overall patient satisfaction in this work was excellent. The findings revealed that majority of patients were satisfied with the quality of nursing care. This is consistent with Agbonjimi et al. (2022); Onianawa and colleagues (2022); Mobolaji-Olajide and colleagues (2020); Folami et al. (2019); and Karaca and colleague (2018) that patients were excellently satisfied with the quality of nursing care and services during their stay in the hospital. However, previous studies done by Dildar et al. (2020); Nebisu and colleagues (2020); and Obi et al. (2018) had contradictory findings with the present study which patients' satisfaction was low. This may be due to the disparity in patient sample size. Many studies have shown that quality of care from nurses is an indicator of patient's satisfaction. Therefore, this illustrates how the patient's satisfaction with the care provided by nurses directly reflects the level of care he or she receives. The study found that quality of care perceived by nurse managers showed high mean percentage compliance. This was assigned under the following factors environmental factors (65.3%), organizational factors (63.2%) and nurse-related factors (68.1%). It is important to note that high mean percentages of the quality of care as identified in this study is evident in the background of high level of patients satisfaction. These findings correspond with works by Xiaolu et al. (2023); Weldetsadik and colleagues (2019); Gaalan et al. (2019); and Liu et al. (2017) evaluated the impact of environmental factors on quality of care. Also the findings from this study is comparable with works by Lateef et al. (2021); and Weldetsadik et al. (2019) evaluated that organizational factors has direct impact on quality of care which is consistent with this study. However Xiaolu and colleagues (2023) showed that organizational factors has indirect effect on quality of care. Furthermore the findings of this study are comparable with works done by Lateef and colleague (2021); and Gaalan et al. (2019) that nurse-related factors have effect on quality of nursing care.

Implications of Findings to Nursing Practice

It has been demonstrated that low job satisfaction, inevitably affects the nurse's wellbeing and leads to high job turnover. Therefore, to mitigate this, employers of nursing staff in public sector may need to improve all components of job satisfaction as found in this study. It also helps to understand the possible role of quality of care in patients' satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Nurses in the study area demonstrated mildly poor job satisfaction. Patients on the other hand were well satisfied with level of health care rendered. This suggests that there is no significant association how well a nurse is satisfied with his or her job and the nursing care he or she delivers. On the other hand recruited patients in this study were well satisfied with the care they received. Also no significant association was demonstrated between the quality of care delivered and how well patients are satisfied with the care they received. This therefore suggests that any change in the determinants of nurse job satisfaction may perhaps not necessarily influence a significant change in how well a patient is satisfied with the quality of care he or she receives.

RECOMMENDATION

Despite low job satisfaction of nurses, they still rendered quality care to patients. However this may possibly not linger for a long time. Therefore,

1. Hospital management should provide and improve the welfare of nurses.
2. Provision of resources and equipment in the hospital for nurses to work with.
3. Provision of conducive and safe environment for the nurses.
4. Government should ensure effective implementation of policies for nurse's remuneration and benefits.

Limitations and Further Research

The study did not explore the depth of knowledge on the recruited patients have about standard of care they received which might influence the outcome of patients satisfaction. This work did not fully explore the awareness and depth of knowledge of standard quality of care in nurses ranked below the head nurses. This study took place in single tertiary teaching hospital of a locality which may not be necessarily reflective of the true outcome of the same study throughout in Nigeria if carried out in two or more tertiary health institutions. Finally further studies can examine the relationship between nurse's job satisfaction and patient's satisfaction.

REFERENCES

- Agbojinmi, L. M., Ayorinde, A. M. and Gbenga-Epebinu, M. A. (2022). Assessment of Patients' Satisfaction with Nursing Care in Babcock University Teaching Hospital, Ilishan-Remo Ogun State Nigeria. *International Journal of Nursing, Midwife and health related Cases*, 8 (3), 34-44.
- Amporfrol, D.A., Boah, M., Yingqi, S., Wabo, T. M. C., Zhao, M., Nkondjock, V. R. N., & Wu, Q. (2021). Patient's satisfaction with healthcare delivery in Ghana. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21, 722.
- Asima, F., Robina, K., Muhammad, H., Ali, W., & Syed, A.G. (2017). Impact of Job Satisfaction on Quality of Care among Nurses on the Public Hospital of Lahore. *Pakistan Saudi Journal of Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 3 (6A), 511-519.
- Asuquo, E. O., Imaledo, J. A., Onyekwelu, C. T., Abara, N. L., & Agugua, C. C. (2017). Job Satisfaction Among Nurses in the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Central African Journal of Public Health*, 3(1), 1-7.
- Archibong, M. (2023). Leadership Styles of Nurse Managers and job Satisfaction. *PubMed Central*.
- Ayalew, F., Kibwana, S., Shawula, S., Misganaw, E., Abbose, Z., Roosmalen, J.V., Stekelenburg, J., Kim, Y. M., Teshome, M., & Damtew, W. M. (2019). Understanding job satisfaction and motivation among nurses in public health facilities of Ethiopia: A cross sectional study. *BMC Nursing*, 46(18), 2-13.

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- Ashwaq, T., Al-Ahmadi., & Sabah, M. M. (2022). Organizational Citizenship Behaviour and Job Satisfaction from the Nurses' Perspective. *Evidence-Based Nursing Research*, 4(1), 17-25.
- Buttel, P., Hendler, R., & Daley, J. (2007). *Quality in Healthcare: Concepts and Practice*.
- Chegni, Z., Janati, A., Asghari-Jafarabadi, M., & Khosravizadeh, O. (2019). Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Justice and Self-efficacy among Nurses.
- Dildar, M., Imran, W. A., & Sehrish, N. (2020). Levels of Patient satisfaction with Nursing Care in public Sector Tertiary Care Hospitals of Peshawar Pakistan: A Cross-sectional descriptive Study. *AJAHS* 5(2).
- Elsherbeny, E.E., & El-Masry, R. (2018). Job Satisfaction among Nurses Working in Mansoura University Hospital: Effect of Socio-Demographic and Work Characteristics. *Egyptian Journal of Occupational Medicine*, 42(2), 227-240.
- Folami, O. A., & Odeyemi, O. (2019). Assessment of Patients Satisfaction with Nursing Care in Selected Wards of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital. *Biomedical Journal of Scientific & Technical Research*.
- Galan, K., Kunaviktikul, W., Akkadechanunt, T., Wichaikhum, O. A., & Turale, S. (2019). Factors predicting quality of nursing care among nurses in tertiary care hospitals in Mongolia. *International Nursing Review*, 66(2), 176-182.
- Hakami, A., Almutairi, H., Otaibi, R. A., Otaibi, T. A., & Battal, A. A. (2020). The Relationship between Nurses Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment. *Health Science Journal*.
- Kabita, P., Sarita, K. and Bidhya, B. (2022). Factors affecting Job Satisfaction among Nurses Working at Western Regional Hospital Pokhara. *Medical Journal of Pokhara Academy of Health Sciences*, 5 (1), 457-464.
- Karaca, A. and Durna, Z. (2019). Patient satisfaction with the quality of nursing care. *Wiley Nursing Open*.
- Kever, R. T., Oyibo, S. S., Ukende, J. F., Damkor, P. L., Gana, A. M., & Danlami, S. (2018). Survey of Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction among Nurses in Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital. *Asian Journal of Research in Nursing and Health*, 1(1), 1-4.
- Lateef, A., & Mhlongo, E. M. (2021). Challenges for Nurses in Providing Patient-Centered Care in Rural Primary Health Care Clinics in Nigeria. *Scientific Research Journal*, 11, 772-793.

Columbia Journal Health Education and Nursing

Research Article

- Malalasekara, L. I., & Sivalogathan, V. (2020). Factors influencing Job satisfaction of Nurses Attached to national Institute of Nephrology Dialysis and Transplant. *Management Issues* 5 (1).
- Manzoor, F., Wei, L., Hussain, A., Asif, M., & Shah, S. I. A. (2019). Patient Satisfaction with Health Care Services: An Application of Physician's Behaviour as a Moderator. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16, 3318.
- Mobolaji-Olajide, O. M., Adereti, S. C., Odutayo, P. O., & Adejumo, P. O. (2020). In-patient satisfaction with nursing care: Outcome measurement in a tertiary health facility in Lagos Nigeria. *International journal of Africa Nursing Sciences*, 13.
- Mousazadeh, S., Yektatalab, S., Momennasab, M., & Parvizy, S. (2019). Job Satisfaction Challenges of Nurses in the Intensive Care Unit: A Qualitative Study. *Risk Management and Healthcare Policy*. <https://www.dovepress.com>
- Ndubuisi, S. F., Makata, N. E., Anieche, J. E., & Umunnah, J. O. (2023). Job satisfaction among Nurses in Tertiary Health Institutions in Edo State Nigeria. *Journal of Biomedical Investigation*, 11(1), 81- 89.
- Nebsu, A., Abdulafiz, A. E., & Musse, T. (2020). Level of Patient satisfaction with inpatient services and its determinants: A Study of a Specialized Hospital in Ethiopia. *PubMed Central*.
- Njaka, S., Oko, C. C., & Njaka, C. (2020). Job Satisfaction and the Associated Factors amongst Nurses in Southeastern Nigeria: Cross Sectional Study. *International Journal of Healthcare and Medical Sciences*, 6(4), 57-63.
- Nsikala, J., Kanste, O., Tomietto, K., Miettunen, J., Tuomikoski, A., Kyngas, H., & Mikkonen, K. (2020). Interventions to improve nurses job satisfaction: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Leading Global Nursing Research*
- Obi, I. E., Ndu, A. C., Agu, K. A., Omotowo, B. I., Agunwa, C. C., & Idoko, A. C. (2018). Patient's satisfaction with services at a tertiary hospital in south-east Nigeria. *PubMed Central*, 30(4), 270-275.
- Olajide, A. O., Sowunmi, C. O., Adeleke, B. O., Ojo, A., Ogunmodede, E.O., & Ajibade, B. L. (2020). Intinsic and Extrinsic factors Influencing Job Satisfaction among Nurses Working in two Selected Government Owned Hospital in Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of Medical Science and Clinical Research*, 8(4), 448-501.

Columbia Journal Health Education and Nursing

Research Article

- Onianwa, P. O., Ike, E. U. and Kuforji, B. (2022). Assessment of Patients' Satisfaction with Nursing Care in a Tertiary Hospital in South West Nigeria. *International Journal of caring Sciences*, 15(2), 1415.
- Orukwogu, U., & Kue, J. B. (2022). Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Tertiary Health Care Centers in Port Harcourt Rivers State Nigeria. *IPS Journal of Management and Administration*, 1(1), 1-6.
- Samson-Akpan, P. E., Edet, O. B., Ojong, I. N., & Asuquo, E. F. (2015). Job satisfaction among Nurses in Public Hospitals in Calabar, Cross River State Nigeria. *American Journal of Nursing Science*, 4(4), 231-237.
- Suparman, S., & Anisah, A. (2023). Nurses' Job Satisfaction and Leadership Styles in a Public Hospital: A Systematic Review. *UNEJe-Proceeding*, 306-313.
- Torkula, T. T. (2020). Challenges in Quality Care Delivery in Tertiary Health Facilities in North- Central Nigeria. Published PhD Dissertation, Department of Nursing Science, Walden University.
- Tengah, S. A., & Otieno, O. J. (2019). Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction among Nurses in Public Health Facilities in Mombasa Kwale and Kilifi counties Kenya. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 6(5), 128-144.
- Umoke, M., Umoke, P. C. I., Nwimo, I. O., Nwalieji, C. A., Onwe, R N, Nwafor, E. I., & Olaoluwa, A. S. (2020). Patients' satisfaction with quality of care in general hospitals in Ebonyi State, Nigeria, using SERVQUAL Theory. *SAGE Open Medicine*, 8, 1-9.
- Wali, R., Aljohani, H., Shakir, M., Jaha, A., & Alhindi, H. (2023). Job Satisfaction among Nurses Working in King Abdul Aziz Medical City Primary Health Care Centers: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Cureus*, 15(1). 33672 Weldetsadik, A.Y., Gishu, T., Tekleab, A.M., Asfaw, Y.M., Legesse, T.G., & Demas, T. (2019). Quality of nursing care and nurses' working environment in Ethiopia: Nurses' and physicians' perception. *International Journal of Africa Nursing Sciences*, 10, 131135.
- Xiaolu, X., Wipada, K., Kulwadee, A., & Orn-Anong, W. (2023). Causal Modelling of Factors Influencing Quality of Care in China. *Pacific Rim International journal of Nursing Research*, 27(3), 417-430.
- Ylitomanen, T. (2021). Nurse-nurse collaboration and job satisfaction: A mixed method study of Finnish and Norwegian nurses perceptions. Published PhD Dissertation, Department of Nursing, University of Eastern Finland